

FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF HERBAL CAPSULE FROM NATURAL HERBS USED AS RESPIRATORY STIMULANTS

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ABSTRACT

Herbal remedies can help treat and prevent respiratory infections and other respiratory issues. These remedies can work by reducing inflammation, boosting the immune system, or clearing mucus. Plant-based formulations are very cost-effective and have fewer adverse effects when used to treat ailments in herbal medicine. Considering these approach research study aimed as formulation and evaluation of herbal capsule from natural herbs used as respiratory stimulants. To cure the respiratory infection by herbs like *Azadirachta indica*, *Curcuma longa*, *Ocimum Sanctum*, *Eugenia caryophyllata*, *Zingiber officinalis* and *Trachyspermum ammi* used for this study. To achieve this objective the poly herbal crude drus were extracted by using hydroalcoholic solvent taken in ratio of 70:30 (ethanol: distilled water). Wet granulation technique with a starch(8.5%w/w) slurry were used for granule preparation. The evaluation parameters such as organoleptic evaluation, powder microscopic analysis of the poly-herbal crude drugs material and physical property analysis such as bulk density, tapped density; compressibility index and angle of repose for the formulated capsules were done. Granules in a “light brown” colour habing bitter taste packed in “00” size yellow capsules. Each poly- herbal capsule was having 500mg. The formulated poly-herbal capsule shows 70.71% CDR in 30min.

KEYWORDS: Poly-herbal capsule, evaluation parameter, physical property, Yellow color, size “00, powder microscopy.

INTRODUCTION

Polyherbal capsules are becoming increasingly popular due to their holistic health benefits, natural healing properties, and minimal side effects compared to synthetic drugs.

The demand is driven by several key factors: Synergistic Therapeutic Effects, Increasing Preference for Natural & Herbal Medicin, Wide Range of Applications, Ayurveda & Traditional Medicine Recognition, Rising Demand for Preventive Healthcare,

Minimal Side Effects & Better Toleranc & Convenient Dosage Form.

Herbal plants are most important for mankind for treatment and management of diseases. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), “natural plants are a plant having more bioactive molecules that have been reported their therapeutic benefits, or which are mother sources of chemo-pharmaceutical semi-synthesis.” Such medicinal plants are in highly demand by the pharmaceutical companies for their bioactive ingredients

Medicinal plants have been reported worldwide in traditional medicines for the treatment of various chronic diseases. According to various reports estimated that even modern time approximately 65-75% of the World's populations depend on medicinal plants for treatment and management of diseases.

Herbal plants and their parts are employed in a variety of therapeutic systems for the treatment of ailments, including homoeopathy, Chinese medicine, Unani medicine, and Ayurvedic medicine.. The quality and purity of the herbal product must be ensured. These standardised herbal products improve the quality of plant medicine and raise its acceptability and export quality in the global market.

Poly-herbal formulation is a great idea that is suited and appropriate for the treatment and management of chronic diseases like cancer. Many studies have been reported with positive findings; however more research is needed to produce promising natural products. Therefore our goal of our current research was development and standardization of raw materials used in the poly-herbal formulation based on organoleptic, powder microscopy and physical property standardization.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Azadirachta indica, Curcuma longa, Ocimum Sanctum, Eugenia caryophyllata, Zingiber officinalis and Trachyspermum ammi. were among the plants collected from the local market of Balaghat (M.P.). The plants materials are verified by Botanist, of Govt. J.S.T. College, Balaghat, (MP). Herbal crude drugs were used to make the poly-herbal formulation. Required all of the necessary chemicals and reagents were of analytical grade purchased and used.

Standardization of poly-herbal crude drugs organoleptic evaluation

The organoleptic characters such as colour, odour, and taste were evaluated by spreading the powder on a clean dry sheet and investigated through the magnifying lens by repeated observation.

Powder microscopy analysis

The powder samples was treated with phloroglucinol (2% w/v) in ethanol (90%) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (1:1) and studied for their components of diagnostic

value. After combining with glycerin, a sufficient amount of coarsely powdered medication was put on a glass slide. All observations were made with ocular10x and 40x objectives, and diagnostic characteristics were photographed. Powder microscopy was used to look for lignified structures such as stone cells, calcium oxalate crystals, starch granules, epidermal cells, xylem fibres, tracheids, parenchyma cells, cuticular cell walls, essential oils, resins, lipids, and fatty oil in a poly-herbal combination.

Other parameters of standardization of poly-herbal crude drugs

Other parameters of standardization of poly-herbal crude drugs are moisture content; total ash value, water soluble ash, acid insoluble ash, heavy metals, water soluble extractive, alcohol soluble extractive, and pH were among the physicochemical parameters of raw materials assessed according to WHO criteria.

pH value: A digital pH meter was used to determine the pH of a1, percent poly-herbal crude drugs solution by using digital pH meter.

Limit test for heavy metals: Pharmacopoeia approaches were used for qualitative heavy metal estimation of arsenic and lead.

Extract of poly-herbal crude drugs combination

Plant materials were purchased from local market at Balaghat, Madhya Pradesh, India's for the extraction of poly-herbal materials. The powdered poly-herbal plant materials was separately weighed and were taken in ratio Azadirachta indica 75mg, Curcuma longa 75mg, Ocimum Sanctum 75mg, Eugenia caryophyllata 75mg, Zingiber officinalis 25mg and Trachyspermum ammi 25mg and mixed well. Then after prepared poly-herbal crude drugs mixture were dipped in hydro alcoholic solvent. The extraction hydroalcoholic solvent was taken in ratio of 70:30 (ethanol: distilled water). This containers was shaken regularly basis for 15 days. The solvent was filtered and evaporated at 40 °C in a rotary vacuum evaporator. The dried poly-herbal hydro alcoholic extract (PHAE) was obtained after filtering and evaporation. The poly-herbal extract was packed in an air tight container and kept in a cool place for further studies.

Phyto chemical test

The phyto chemical investigation of poly-herbal hydro alcoholic extract (PHAE) was performed, for the investigation of secondary metabolites such as alkaloids, carbohydrates, flavonoids, tannins, and steroids.

1. Alkaloid Detection Tests

Alkaloids are nitrogen-containing compounds that can be detected using the following tests:

a. Wagner's Test

Reagents: Wagner's reagent (Iodine in Potassium Iodide)
Procedure: Add a few drops of Wagner's reagent to the plant extract.

Observation: Formation of a brown or reddish-brown precipitate indicates the presence of alkaloids.

b. Dragendorff's Test

Reagents: Dragendorff's reagent (Potassium Bismuth Iodide solution)

Procedure: Add a few drops of Dragendorff's reagent to the extract.

Observation: Formation of an orange or reddish precipitate indicates alkaloids.

c. Mayer's Test

Reagents: Mayer's reagent (Potassium Mercuric Iodide)
Procedure: Add a few drops of Mayer's reagent to the extract.

Observation: Formation of a creamy white precipitate confirms the presence of alkaloids.

2. Tannin Detection Tests

Tannins are polyphenolic compounds and can be detected by the following tests:

a. Ferric Chloride Test

Reagents: 5% Ferric Chloride (FeCl₃) solution
Procedure: Add a few drops of FeCl₃ solution to the extract.

Observation: A greenish-black or blue-black coloration indicates the presence of tannins.

b. Lead Acetate Test

Reagents: 10% Lead Acetate solution
Procedure: Add a few drops of lead acetate solution to the extract.

Observation: Formation of a white or yellowish precipitate indicates tannins.

c. Gelatin Test

Reagents: 1% Gelatin solution
Procedure: Mix the extract with gelatin solution.
Observation: Precipitation indicates the presence of tannins.

3. Flavonoid Detection Tests

Flavonoids are polyphenolic secondary metabolites and can be detected by the following tests:

a. Alkaline Reagent Test

Reagents: Sodium Hydroxide (NaOH) solution
Procedure: Add a few drops of NaOH solution to the extract, followed by dilute Hydrochloric Acid (HCl).
Observation: A yellow color that disappears upon acidification confirms the presence of flavonoids.

b. Shinoda Test (Magnesium and HCl Test)

Reagents: Magnesium ribbon, Concentrated HCl.
Procedure: Add a small piece of magnesium ribbon to the extract, followed by a few drops of concentrated HCl.
Observation: A pink or red coloration indicates flavonoids.

c. Lead Acetate Test

Reagents: 10% Lead Acetate solution
Procedure: Add lead acetate solution to the extract.
Observation: Formation of a yellow precipitate confirms the presence of flavonoids

FORMULATION**Preparation of formulation by wet granulation method**

The poly-herbal formulation preparation began with hit and trials, with several ratios of binders and quantities of lubricants and preservatives being selected, before the technique was finally refined. Poly-herbal hydro alcoholic extract (PHAE) of *Azadirachta indica*, *Curcuma longa*, *Ocimum Sanctum*, *Eugenia caryophyllata*, *Zingiber officinalis* and *Trachyspermum ammi* were coarsely powdered (sieve40), mixed in a ratio of 2:2:1, and used to make capsules using wet granulation technique with a starch(8.5%w/w) slurry. The starch(8.5%w/w) slurry was added in poly-herbal blends by geometric dilution, to obtain a homogenous damp mass. The damp mass was sieved into granules using a sieve of aperture no 80 then after damp granules were dried to obtain a constant weight. The dried granules were then screened using aperture no 120 and 1 % magnesium stearate was used to lubricate the granules. The granules from the optimized batch (20 % lactose) were then put in yellow size "00" capsules in a capsule filling machine. The capsules were then removed and placed in poly bags, which were then tagged, and the samples were analysed according to the testing standards. Each poly-herbal capsule was having 500mg.

Name of Ingredient	Quantity
<i>Azadirachta indica</i>	75mg
<i>Curcuma longa</i>	75mg
<i>Ocimum Sanctum</i>	75mg
<i>Eugenia caryophyllata</i>	75mg
<i>Zingiber officinalis</i>	25mg
<i>Trachyspermum ammi</i>	25mg
Ethanol: Distilled Water	70:30%
starch	8.5% w/w (42mg)
magnesium stearate	1% (5mg)

Lactose	20% (100mg)
Capsule shell	“00”size

Physical property analysis of poly-herbal granules

Bulk density, tap density and Carr's index

In a 50ml measuring cylinder, a weighted quantity (15g) of poly herbal powdered ingredients was placed and the initial volume was recorded (v₀). After 50 taps, the contents were volume checked and the powdered volumes were recorded (v₅₀). This procedure was done three times, with the average determined and recorded. Fluff density (B.D.) is defined as the weight of powder divided by the volume of powder in millilitres.

T.D.=weight of powder/volume occupied by powder

Tapped density- Fluff density/ Tapped density*100=Carr's index (C.I.)

Carr's index values below 15 indicate excellent flowing material, whereas values between 20 and 30 indicate poor flowing material.

Angle of repose: On a burette stand, a funnel was mounted at a specific height (1.5, 2.5, 3.5 cm). On the table, a white paper was placed beneath the funnel. Slowly, the powdered substance made its way through the funnel, eventually forming a pile. The pile's radius was calculated.

The powder material's angle of repose was computed using the formula: $\tan \theta = h/r = \tan (h/r)$.

Where h is the pile's height and r is its radius. Angles of repose of 30° normally indicate a freely flowing material, while angles of 40° usually indicate a poorly flowing material.

Hausner's ratio: The basic approach is to tap the powder until no more volume changes occur and measure the unsettled apparent volume, V₀, and the final tap volume, V_f. The following is how the Hausner's ratio was calculated:

T.D./B.D. is Hausner's ratio. Between 1.00 to 1.11, Hausner's ratio indicates excellent flow, whereas greater than 1.60 indicates extremely poor flow.

Capsule Filling and Packing: A manual capsule filling machine was used to fill the capsules in a controlled environment (25°C and less than 60% relative humidity) (300capsules in a single operation). [Mahto et al., 2022, Beg et al., 2021, Jayachandra et al., 2019]Capsules containing 500mg or more, no more than two capsules should deviate by more than 5%, and none should depart by more than 10%.The uniformity of weight test revealed that all of the medication capsules had weights that were substantially within the permissible range (Table 4). It suggests that pre-encapsulation procedures like granulation and filling the hard gelatin body were completed precisely and consistently. The filled capsules were de-dusted, sealed, and kept in bottles containing silica gel packets for moisture-free storage.

Capsule evaluation: The poly-herbal capsules were compared to Indian pharmacopoeial standards for their

description, microbiological load, and uniformity of dosage units, weight fluctuation, disintegration time, and moisture content.

Microbial load analysis: Microbial load analysis performed to ensure that the poly- herbal capsules were safe to use, and was checked to see if the total aerobic viable count, yeasts, and moulds were within the prescribed limits, and that the microorganisms Escherichia coli, Clostridia, Salmonellae, Shigella, Pseudomonas, and Staphylococcus were not present in the final formulation.

Weight variation: Twenty capsules were weighed separately, and the average weight was computed. Average weight-individual weight/ Average weight x 100 = Weight variance.

Moisture level: The amount of moisture in the air was measured using automatic Karl Fischer titration equipment.

Uniformity in Drug Content: An essential quality control test in the evaluation of a finished pharmaceutical product is the homogeneity of the drug content. In order to give the patient the proper amount and prevent under- and overdosing, it makes sure that a constant dose of the active ingredient is maintained between and among production batches. Under dosing will result in less than ideal results, while overdoing will have unfavorable side effects on the user.

Dissolution: The dissolution of a poly-herbal formulation preparation was investigated. In some situations, dissolution is a useful Technique for estimating absorption and bioavailability, and it can even be used to replace clinical tests in determining medication bioequivalence. Six capsules were employed in basket-style dissolution equipment using distilled water as the dissolution media. The speed was set at 50 rpm for 1hour, and the sample was drawn every 10minutes, with the amount of dissolved active ingredient in the solution calculated as a percentage dissolved in that time.

Stability: The stability profile of the developed poly-herbal capsule formulation was investigated under accelerated temperatures, humidity, and light intensities. Extrinsic aspects such as physical, chemical, and therapeutic changes in the poly-herbal capsule were studied, and the results were determined using the following parameters.

Light: To assess powder material deterioration, the developed poly-herbal capsule formulation was stored in various intensities of light, including sunrays, fluorescent(tube) light, UV, and infrared light.

Temperature: The effect of temperature on the stability of the created poly-herbal capsule formulation was investigated by holding all capsules at different temperatures for 30 minutes, 1, 3, and 6 hours at ambient, 35°C, 50°C, 55°C, and 65°C.

Humidity: The influence of humidity on the stability of the capsule was tested by using the full capsule at four different humidity percentages, namely 30%, 50%, 70%, and 90%.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Poly-herbal capsules were prepared using eight different crude drugs from different families, as well as different morphological plant sections and phyto- constituents. The most important aspect of the created poly-herbal formulation standardization is quality, safety, and reproducibility. It encompasses the complete process, beginning with the harvesting of plants and other raw

materials and ending with the development of a finished product using firm gelatin capsules, a standardized development of a poly-herbal mixture was developed in this study. The intensive investigation of the formulation in the alternative system of medicine is the need of the hour to fill the lacuna in the quality control of herbal drugs. The formulated poly herbal capsule is investigated for its organoleptic evaluation. The characters showed pale yellow colour with characteristic odour and bitter taste.

Standardization of poly-herbal crude drugs Organoleptic evaluation

Organoleptic evaluation are shown in Table 1

Powder microscopy analysis

Poly-herbal combination powder microscopy study performed and concluded in Fig. 1

Figure 1: Powder characteristics of plants materials used in poly-herbal formulation.

a: starch grains; b: prismatic crystal of calcium oxalate; c: fragment of fibres and annular vessel; d: parenchymatous cells with anomocytic stomata; e: fibre (reticulate); f: pitted vessel attached with bunch of fibres; g: fragments of medullary rays; h: cork cells (lignified).

Phyto chemical investigation

Poly-herbal extract were investigated phyto chemically. In the case of herbal medicine, thorough and full identification is one of the most crucial parameters because if the herbs are not properly identified, the formulation will not deliver the desired benefits. It was important to test the presence of distinct chemical compositions of the herbs before the blends were placed

into the capsule dosage form. Phytochemical tests are commonly used to detect the presence of various bioactive compounds in plant extracts, including alkaloids, tannins, and flavonoids. Here's how you can perform these tests on the extract of **PHAE**. It was indicating that this combination is suited for therapeutic activity. Alkaloids, Glycosides, Sterols, Triterpenes and saponins were detected in poly-herbal extract.

The results of these phyto chemical tests revealed the presence of alkaloids, tannins, and flavonoids in the extract of PHAE. The results of phyto chemical investigations are shown in Table 2.

Tablet 2: Chemical composition of eight herbal plants used in the preparation of PHAE.

Chemical composition	Poly-herbal formulation
Proteins	-
Lipids	-
Alkaloids	+
Glycosides	+
Sterols	+
Triterpenes	+
Tannins/Flavonoids	++
Saponins	+
Steroids	-

Standardization of prepared poly-herbal crude drugs

Moisture content, total ash value, water soluble ash, acid insoluble ash, heavy metals, water soluble extractive, alcohol soluble extractive, and acidity were among the physicochemical parameters of raw materials assessed according to WHO criteria (pH). The results of standardization of prepared poly-herbal crude drugs are shown in Table 1.

Ash value and extractive value: Total ash, water soluble ash, acid soluble ash, and extractive values were obtained using the procedure outlined elsewhere. Loss on drying 2.55 percent, total ash 5.66 percent, acid-insoluble ash 1.28 percent, and water-soluble ash 3.51 percent, water-soluble extractive value 16.72 percent, ethanol-

soluble extractive value 13.38 percent, arsenic not more than 5ppm, microbial load analysis, presence of E.coli (should be absent), presence of salmonella (should be absent), presence of streptococcus (should be absent), presence of pseudomonas (should be absent) and total microbial count of yeast and molds are under limit. The results are shown in Table 1.

Limit test for heavy metals: The Limits for heavy metals were performed as per official Pharmacopeia methods. The heavy metals like as Arsenic and lead was found to be in under limit like Arsenic in 5ppm, and Lead not more than 10ppm, respectively. The results are shown in Table 1.

Test details to be in thesis.

Tablet 1: Standardization of poly-herbal capsule.

Name of the test	Observations
Organoleptic characters	Brown colour powder
Colour	Brown
Odour	Characteristic
Taste	Bitter
Physiochemical parameters	
pH	7.7
Moisture content	1.01%
Average weight	533mg
Weight variation	2.83%
Disintegration time (Mean \pm SEM)	3min25 seconds \pm 0.21
Loss on drying	2.55%
Total ash	5.66%
Acid-insoluble ash	1.28%
Water-soluble ash	3.51%
Water-soluble extractive value	16.72%
Ethanol-soluble extractive value	13.38%
Limits for heavy metals	Complies
Arsenic not more than 5ppm	Complies
Lead not more than 10ppm	Complies
Microbial load analysis	Complies
Total microbial count NMT 1000cfu/g	113cfu/g
Yeast and molds	Nil
Presence of E.coli (should be absent)	Absent
Presence of Salmonella (should be absent)	Absent
Presence of Streptococcus (should be absent)	Absent
Presence of Pseudomonas (should be absent)	Absent

NMT: Not more than Result (n=3) are reported as Mean \pm Standard deviation.

Preparations of poly-herbal extract

Preparation of poly-herbal extract was performed by using hydroalcoholic solvent. The yield of hydroalcoholic extract was found to be 8.1%.

EVALUATION OF POLY-HERBAL CAPSULE FORMULATION**Flow property of powdered extract**

The flow quality of the powder was verified before it was filled into capsules. According to Indian

Pharmacopoeia, the flow property of poly-herbal formulation was found to be the best and within acceptable limits. The results are reported in Table 3 below. The flow property of the blend to be placed in the capsule should be within acceptable limits, as determined by the following parameters. Formulation of a poly-herbal pill that was optimized.

Table 3: Pre formulation parameters.

Parameters	Poly-herbal formulation
Bulk density	0.823g/ml
Tapped density	0.702 g/ml
Carrsindex	14.8023
Hausnersratio	1.16±0.04
Angle of repose	19.040

Evaluation of poly-herbal capsule formulation

Granules in a “light brown” colour packed in “00” size yellow capsules. The poly-herbal capsules were compared to Indian pharmacopeial standards for their description, microbiological load, and uniformity of dosage units, weight fluctuation, and disintegration time. Brown colour, distinctive scent, and taste were discovered to have organoleptic characteristics.

pH value: A digital Ph meter was used to determine the pH and was found to be pH 7.7 of a 1 percent solution.

Microbial load analysis: Microbiological load was found under limit as per WHO guideline limit.

Weight variation: The average weight of prepared poly-herbal formulation was found to be 533mg and weight variation 2.83 percent was found.

Moisture level: The moisture content of prepared poly-herbal formulation was found to be 1.01 percent.

Uniformity in Drug Content: According to official method a poly-herbal capsule passes this test. The poly-herbal capsule formulations are shown the specified acceptance limit and won't result in an under dosing or overdosing effect. The consistency of the drug contents of the prepared capsules was attributed to effective granulation, particle size distribution, and homogeneous filling of the capsule shells. The test results were found to be under limit 85% to 115% range.

Dissolution: The in-vitro approach was used to investigate the optimal poly-herbal dissolving formulation upto 30minutes; the highest cumulative drug release of a bioactive drug molecule is 70.71 percent. The results are shown in Table 4 and Fig.2.

Tablet 4: In-Vitro Dissolution Studies.

Time in Min.	Absorbance A	C=A/0.011 mg/ml	Amount released in microgram=c*volume of dissolution medium	Amount of drugreleased in mg/ml=(c*volume of dissolution medium)/1000	%CDR= (amount of released/Drug concentraion con)*100
5	0.21	105	94500	94.5	27
10	0.252	126	113400	113.4	32.4
15	0.305	152.5	137250	137.25	39.21428571
20	0.405	202.5	182250	182.25	52.07142857
25	0.51	255	229500	229.5	65.57142857
30	0.55	275	247500	247.5	70.71428571

Figure 2: In-vitro %cumulative drug release of poly-herbal capsule.

Moisture level: The moisture content of prepared poly-herbal formulation was found to be 1.01 percent.

Stability: The stability parameters were compared after 30minutes, 1,3, and 6hours of storage under accelerated

temperature, light, and humidity conditions. The observation has been summarised in table 5, 6, and 7 for three Stability parameters, suggesting that there gross physical qualities do not generate any substantial change. The results are shown in Table 5, 6 and Table 7.

Tablet 5: Effect of different intensities of lights on poly-herbal capsules.

Light Source	Sun light	Fluorescence	Tube light	UV Light	Infra-Red (IR)	Lamp Light
Time of Exposure (hours)	1/2 1 3	6 1/2 1 3 6	1/2 1 3	6 1/2 1 3	6 1/2 1 3 6	1/2 1 3 6
500mg poly herbal capsule.....	+					

Tablet 6: Stability test of poly-herbal capsule at different temperature.

		1/2	1	3	6	
Ambient	30°C	-	-	-	-	No change during 6 hours after
Warm(30-40 °C)	35°C	-	-	-	-	No change during 6 hours after
Accelerated	50°C	-	-	-	-	No change during 6 hours after
Accelerated	55°C	-	-	-	+	Degradation start after 4 hours
Accelerated	65°C	-	-	+	+	Degradation start after 2 hours

Tablet 7: Stability of poly herbal capsule at different humidity & temperature.

Temperature	30%	50%	70%	90%
	Humidity	Humidity	Humidity	Humidity
30%	-	-	-	-
35%	-	-	-	-
55%	-	-	+	++
65%	-	-	++	+++

(+) Degradation (-) No Change

In this research work wet granulation process was used to create a poly-herbal combination capsule formulation, which was subsequently tested for quality poly-herbal product. The pre-formulation and formulation investigations of the created poly-herbal capsule solid dosage form were examined since it is highly important regardless of their medicinal content and therapeutic conditions. Angle of repose (a common characterization method for pharmaceutical powder flow), porosity (packing geometry), Carr's index, and Hausner's ratio are some of the preformulation parameters (a measure of the inter-particulate friction). These are helpful tools for creating new poly-herbal formulations.

A value of 30° denotes 'good' flow, whereas a value of >56° denotes 'very bad' flow. The flow was given an 'excellent' rating as a result of this. 14.8023 and 1.160.04 were found to represent the CI and HR, respectively. A material with a lower CI or Hausner ratio has superior flow qualities than one with a higher one.

Powder flow helps to Avoid the costly and time-consuming process of emptying powder s that will not flow out of storage containers as well As assisting in the development of the optimal formulation and improving the product's quality and consistency.

After undergoing phytopharmaceutical review in accordance with pharmacopoeial norms, all eight herbal medications were approved as quality drugs. In-vitro, each poly-herbal capsule weighing 500 mg approx dissolved in 13 minutes. The release of a drug from a solid dosage format in which the substance dissolved in the fluid of the gastrointestinal system is known as drug dissolution. The results showed that all six capsules disintegrated at a rate of 70.71% in 30 minutes. During an invitro investigation, the drug releasing pattern from the capsule shell is used to forecast the releasing sequence. The correlations between in-vitro and in-vivo results are being used to construct a tool for determining drug bioavailability and bioequivalence. The poly-herbal capsule was determined to be almost stable after phyto pharmaceutical investigations and stability testing.

CONCLUSION

The poly-herbal combination of chosen plants was tested and found to be good results. It can be utilizing more accurate methodologies is needed to investigate the contents responsible for the action and the mechanism of this activity. Our findings show that the oral dosage form (500mg capsule according to the Indian Pharmacopeia) standardization parameter of poly-herbal capsule formulation was effectively evaluated by using organoleptic evaluation, powder microscopical evaluation of the raw materials used and the physical property analysis. The results obtained from the study can be utilized as a reference for setting limits for the reference standards for the quality control and quality assurance of the herbal drugs.

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